

OPEN ACCESS TO SCIENTIFIC INFORMATION

HORIZON 2020

= an obligation to grant **immediate, free, permanent and independent online access (open access, OA)** to all peer-reviewed scientific publications related to the project results, when publishing is chosen as a means of dissemination.

The obligation concerns primarily **peer-reviewed scientific research articles**. OA is strongly recommended for other types of scientific publications.

HOW TO FULFILL THE OA OBLIGATION?

Step 1: Deposit publications in a repository

What to deposit? → A machine-readable electronic copy of the publisher version or the final reviewed version of the article (postprint).

🔗 Where to deposit? → A **repository** is an online archive (institutional, disciplinary or multidisciplinary). The [OpenAIRE](#) portal can be used to find a suitable repository or you can use the European Commission's [Zenodo](#) Universal Repository .

🔗 When to deposit? → A copy of the article must be deposited in the repository as soon as possible, and **no later than the date of publication**.

Step 2: Ensure open access to the publication

To ensure OA to the publication, the author must choose **at least one** of the following ways:

🔗 Gold OA – Open access publishing

The author can choose in which open access journal he will publish (full OA or in a [hybrid journal](#)). However, the article must also be deposited in a repository for **long-term preservation**.

🔗 Green OA – Self-archiving

The author grants open access to the article through an **open repository**. It is necessary to comply with the **license conditions of the publisher** and, if necessary, negotiate [an amendment to the OA agreement](#).

€ Financing

Possible publication fees (article processing charges, APC) are eligible costs for the duration of the grant.

More detailed information on open access to scientific information can be found on the website of the [Central Library of Charles University](#). If necessary, contact your [faculty open access librarian](#) or the [Open Science Support Center](#).

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